

CURRICULUM AND PEDAGOGIC APPROACHES IN THE CONTEXT OF INDIAN KNOWLEDGE TRADITION AND THE DRAFT OF NPE-2016

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Abstract

Today, mental setup of learners is changing with the recent technologies. Therefore, Global trends are demanding training of versatility for developing new teaching strategies and ability to contribute knowledge for complex issues like individual goals of learners, physical and mental retardation and inclusion, etc. Here, we are engaging in connecting ideas, changing in preliminary policies with practices and recommendations, and finding research gaps with the help of practitioners (teachers, teacher educators, etc.), policymakers and researchers. In 1968 Indian education system takes a new turn with its first educational policy, known as NPE-1968 (National Policy on Education) with the recommendation to provide directions to the State Governments and local authorities of education to implement educational plans. After that NPE-1986 and PoA-1992 (Programme of Action) (also known as reforms of NPE-1986) came into light with the suggestive strategies to establish Navodaya Vidyalaya for rural talents, to satisfy the needs of schools through operation blackboard, redesigning of courses, training for teachers, education through open and distance learning, promotion of women education and education for disadvantaged sections.

Keywords: Teaching Strategies, Learning Strategies, NPE-1968, NPE-1986, NPE-2016, Indian Knowledge Tradition.

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Introduction

In ashram system, there was no any written curriculum for the future creation of the disciples. But teachers were known as "Guru", "Swami", "Acharya" etc. used new strategies to teach them for preparing them for daily life. The ancient scriptures opine that there was a setup for the practice-based teaching and learning. For example strategy of Chakravayuh was a new pedagogical strategy for the military tactic at that time. Today, the classroom is military ground, where a teacher uses pedagogical strategies for easy and permanent learning. The problem of individual difference has always been. But, the true teacher never gets frustrated, and never takes the road to disappointment. After the independence of India, CABE (Central Advisory Board of Education) set-up a committee on Wardha Education Scheme, also known as Nayee Taleem, this was given by Mahatma Gandhi, for implementation of it. This was reiterated by the CABE in 1944 in Sargent Plan for educational development in India through universalisation of primary education, to improve the quality of education. The report of University Education Commission 1948-49 opined that there is a need for urgent and flexible reform in education to transform it according to the endeavour of the learner and relate it to their life. It also feels that needs and aspirations of the learner make the powerful instrument of social, economic and cultural transformation for the realisation of the national goals. Therefore, to fill these purposes, education should be developed to achieve social and national integration, to increase productivity,

and to accelerate the process of modernisation and cultivate social, moral and spiritual values (Kumar, 1976, pp.153-154.).

Education in India is always being as work of worship. Swami Vivekanand has also declared the characteristic of education in his words that education is not the amount of information to put into brains. Here in the brain, conflicts run which undigest all your life. We must have long life preparing, man makin and character building assimilation of ideas. If you have assimilated some creative ideas and made them the main part of your life and character, then you have more education with knowledge than any man who has got by intellectually a whole library. If education and knowledge are identical with authentic information, the libraries are the greatest sages of the world and encyclopaedias are the greatest Rishis (Thakur, D. & Thakur, D. (1996), pp. 32-33).

Challenges for curriculum

India is known for its greatest old education system. The oldest university Taxila is known for greatest guru Chanakya, whereas biggest Nalanda University for its toughest entrance examination. Even without patents, contributions of the Indian scholars like Charaka for Ayurveda, Susruta for surgery, Aryabhata and Bhaskara for mathematics and astrology, Chanakya for Economics, Patanjali for Yoga and Vatsayayna for philosophy etc. are unforgettable. The Indian education system from ancient to today helped in preserving our ancient culture and knowledge; promoting cultural equity and unity; and infused a positive sense of responsibility for social values. The education system of ancient India has been a source of inspiration to all educational systems of the world, and everywhere it spread its fragrance. Evidently not known but these scholars are the witness of educating by a unique curriculum. Freedom fighters like Gopal Krishna Gokhale, Mahatma Gandhi and Mahatma Jyoti Rao Phule etc. worked for the Indian education system. But after the seven decades, there is no major changes are observed genuinely in Indian education system. The draft of New Education Policy-2016 has tried to focus the deficiencies and challenges faced by our education system with the necessary need to improve quality of teaching and learning. This draft suggests a framework for changing and making education modern by incorporating technology in it without compromising on culture, traditions and heritage of India. The curriculum frameworks prepared by National Council of Educational Research and Training consecutively in 1975, 1988, 2000 and 2005 specify the varieties of its contribution. NCERT, with its known position as a distinctive organisation with huge consent, is faced with enormous challenges for catering to teaching and learning in diverse situations and conditions. The draft of NPE-2016 has attracted attention on following challenges for curriculum –

1. The absence of minimum norms and standards in the provision of schooling facilities, processes and student outcomes, and equity in educational opportunities
2. Lack of professionalisation in educational planning and management
3. The absence of requisite disaggregated data, particularly at sub-national and institutional levels for evidence-based management of education
4. Preparing a curriculum which encourages rote-based learning
5. Malpractices in the examination system

6. Neglect of skill and vocational education
7. Overemphasis on acquiring dead-end qualifications which do not lead to employment
8. Failure to make ICT (Information and Communication Technology) as functionally integral to the management of pedagogy of education
9. Mushrooming of such type of private universities and degree shops which have not been maintaining quality
10. Corruption in institutional management and politicisation of educational institutions
11. Hackneyed status of a big range of higher education institutions
12. The education system has less concentration on the emerging learning areas
13. The education system is unable to respond to the impact of globalisation and the demands of the emerging knowledge-based economy and society
14. The education system is unable to meet the learning needs of diverse groups of learners
15. The education system is unable in linking education with life-skills and the world of work
16. The education system is unable in generating concern relating to sustainable development
17. Less attention to achieve excellence in learning outcomes that are comparable to student learning outcomes in high performing international education systems
18. Complicated procedures to attain objectives of education with a view to revision and upgrading of the curricula

Challenges for pedagogic approaches

The uniqueness of the ancient Indian education system rests upon the uniqueness of the traditional teaching and learning process based on the Gurukul System. The ancient Indian education system had a rich treasure of teaching methods and approaches like Archery, Fencing, Cooking, Politics, Theology, Astronomy, Astrology and Therapeutics with the study of Vedas, Vedangs and Upanishadas. There were many pedagogical techniques were exercised in the ancient Indian traditions by the teachers or Ashram Gurus. The main sources of information are ancient Indian scriptures and description of pedagogical approaches in the Upanishads. Most of the pedagogic approaches were based on teacher-pupil relationship. The child-centred pedagogic approaches are not newly born. In Gurukul System, pupils were trained in life-skills by rigorous training and tough examinations. We know that every pupil cannot be Arjuna itself, but if we are successful in creating a single Dronacharya, then there will be no shortage of Arjunas. Finally, the issue of how best the pedagogical techniques can be used in the modern educational system to create learner-centred education, are discussed in the draft of NPE-2016 as under –

1. Lack of competent and committed teachers, resulting in poor quality of education
2. Substandard quality of teacher education and training
3. Malpractices by teachers in the classroom
4. Neglect of skill and vocational education, overemphasis on acquiring dead-end qualifications which do not lead to employment

5. Lack of knowledge and application of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) in classroom teaching by the teachers
6. Mushroom growth of private coaching classes which are disabling the children from the brain
7. The pursuit of degrees and qualifications at any cost
8. Appointment of unqualified and low paid contractual teachers who are unknown with the teaching and learning strategies and militates against the quality of teaching and learning
9. Failure to inculcate the minimum levels of skills, knowledge, values and attitudes into the children to make them productive citizens of India
10. Less attention on the emerging learning areas
11. Less attention to needs of the learner

12. Less attention to global demand of knowledge

13. Unable in linking education with daily life routine
14. Unable to implement the objectives of sustainable development
15. Unable in completely linking disadvantaged sections to the mainstream of education system
16. Unable to prepare curriculum according to global needs
17. Less success in preventing education from escaping

Inputs on ancient Indian education system

Indian history gives information of development of education system from Vedic Period, where the study of all four Vedas as Rigveda, Yajurveda, Samveda, and Atharvaveda used to be, we take account of educational thoughts manifested in different scriptures. Ancient Indian literature is divided into Shruti and Smriti element of learning and teaching. Shruti means listening or hearing which consist of supernatural texts and scripts like Vedas and Upanishads, and can be transmitted orally as such. Smriti means that are remembered. These are supernaturally written scriptures, originated from human authors and contains codes of conduct for human life. For examples Mahabharata, Ramayana, Smriti, and Samhitas etc. The whole human life was divided into four Ashrams, in which Brahmacharya Ashram (Birth to 25 years), was to gain educational qualification. Education was started from From the Upnayan or Vidyarambh Sanskaar, which was from 5 to 11-12 years. Before and after the independence, many efforts were done by the freedom fighter and education experts. Various committees, commissions like Radhakrishnan Commission for higher education, Mudaliar Commission for secondary education, Kothari Commission for whole education in India, NPE-1968, NPE-1986, PoA-1992, NCF-1975, 1988, 2000 and 2005, NCFTE-2009 were established, which gave particular recommendations by understanding needs of society and various communities etc. It was an unfortunate part of these documents was that it was nowhere seen that what we can learn from our glorious past. The draft of NPE-2016 favours that the underlying aim of education in ancient India was not to give only knowledge as preparation for life in this world or life beyond, but for self-actualisation and complete realisation of self.

Inputs on culture, values and heritage

In ancient India, during the Rigvedic period, societies were matriarchal. Diverse traditions were the part of families. Societies promote various cultures. Therefore, the education system too became multicultural. The draft of NPE-2016 also advocates education with Indian values. It is well known that India has suffered the serious problem of terrorism and fundamentalism. Today it is needed to prepare civilians for contributing peace, harmony and mutual-trust to build a civilised cultural society. Education is the Brahmsra which can control the mind by insight. Because education gives the sense of distinguishing right and wrong. For boosting secularism and value education in Indian society and also in its civilians, the recommendations of the Chavan Committee Report, which is also known as the report of Ethics Committee, are principally relevant. Its recommendations referred to the following –

(Point No. 8) "Truth (Satya), Righteous conduct (Dharma), Peace (Shanti), Love (Prem), and Nonviolence (Ahimsa) are the core and basic universal values which can be identified as the foundation stone on which the value-based education programme can be build-up. These five are indeed universal values and respectively represent the five domains of human personality: intellectual, physical, emotional, psychological and spiritual. They also are correspondingly co-related with the five major objectives of education, namely, knowledge, skills, balance, vision, and identity."

(Point No. 13) "Another aspect that must be given some thought is religion, which is the most misused and misunderstood concept. The process of making the students acquainted with the basics of all religions, the values inherent therein and also a comparative study of the philosophy of all religions should begin at the middle stage in schools and continue up to the university level. Students have to be made aware that the basic concept behind of every religion is common, only the practices differ. Even if there are differences of opinion in certain areas, people have to learn to coexist and carry no hatred against any religion."

The draft of NPE-2016 advocates for enabling the students for the globalised and digital world by familiarising with the basics of the Constitution of India, its preamble and chapters of Fundamental Rights and Duties in the frame of India's traditions, culture and heritage.

Inputs on the man-making process

During the Rigvedic period, in Ashramas, every student was treated equally without any discrimination. Every pupil was prepared through same and tough examination process for future. The man-making process was fully standardized at that time. Therefore, Baudhayan, Aryabhata, Brahmgupta, Bhaskaracharya, Kanad, Varahamihira, Nagarjuna, Susruta, Charak, Patanjali etc. were not born but made by the teachers of them. The draft of NPE-2016 gives view to inculcate key qualities and attitudes from Indian culture like punctuality, regularity, cleanliness, self-discipline, sense of duty, responsibility, accountability, desire to serve, creativity, respect towards women and character construction. Therefore, it is necessary to maintain school environment, enabling teachers for social values with imparting friendliness, compassion, cooperativeness, courage and

curiosity to get the rights. The aim of education should be of developing pride in India and in being an Indian. Indian society is characterised not only by multi-cultural, multi-lingual and multi-religious diversity, regional disparities but also by inequalities of income, wealth, opportunity and access to resources. So, education should foster learning about our ancient history, culture-heritage and traditions to prepare man with characteristics of peace, tolerance, secularism and national integration.

Teacher education

When the learner comes to the school, He does not know about the functioning of the school, classroom and behaviour of teachers. Indian Vedas, Upanishads and epics give information about the ideal image of a teacher, his characteristics, and various teaching strategies with multidimensional techniques which are known as Vidyas or Chakras. Today teacher education is measured as weakest part of the whole education system of India. It is a universal truth that we have the pride of being a world Guru. Lamarck is best known for his Theory of Inheritance of Acquired Characteristics, "If an organism changes during life in order to adapt to its environment, those changes are passed on to its offspring." Therefore, we have forgotten that the Indian mind has developed from the Sanskrit language, in which there is no place for single error including exceptions.

Every Government is reforming education policies with less focus on teacher education. Here is a need to have a brand new perception for preparing dynamic teachers. Lee Elliot Major, Director of Policy and Development of the Sutton Trust in What Makes Great Teaching said, "It's a scandal that we are so concerned with the learning of pupils, yet neglect the professional development of teachers themselves. Good quality teachers are the agents of social mobility able to transform the achievement pupils from poorer backgrounds. This research review debunks many of the teaching myths but also reveals the core lessons for schools to help them develop great teachers." The National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education-2009 (NCFTE) includes guidelines of RTE Act 2009 with social and moral ethics, training of brain through arts and crafts, music, physical Education and, life skills including inclusive education to ensure overall development of all type of learners.

Report of NPE 2016 in favour of human knowledge described that "Technology alone cannot be the solution to the problem of poor quality of education; the human factor is equally, if not more, important. The Committee recognises that the teacher is the pivot around which the education system revolves; sadly, we have not succeeded in attracting good students to the teaching profession; added to that, most teacher education courses have little substance. The Committee has made several recommendations to improve the quality of teacher training and education because, without good teachers, there can be no quality education." (p.4) Therefore, policies should be reframed by earmarking all quality standards and needs of the teacher also. There is a need for a separate board for accreditation and assessment quality of teacher education and teacher education institutions. The draft of NPE-2016 indicates the following recommendations for teacher education –

1. Independent mechanism for teacher recruitment – the recent TET mechanism (with

- appropriate safeguards) will ensure good quality recruitment of teachers
2. Creation of an Autonomous Teacher Recruitment Board
3. Revamp of teacher education system and the introduction of a four-year integrated B.Ed. Course or a two-year B.Ed. Course after graduation
4. Effective monitoring of teacher performance, with built-in incentive systems
5. New transparent system for approval, affiliation and regular evaluation of new institutions, with transparent processes, based on clearly established principles, with full public disclosure
6. Appropriate use of Information Technology in every aspect of governance of the sector

What should be incorporated in NPE-2016

Problems of education existed worldwide, and agencies of education are trying to resolve these problems. In this direction in 1993, UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation) established a 15 members' committee, under the chairmanship of Jacques Delors entitled "Learning: The treasure within". The report envisages that if education is to succeed in its tasks, curriculum as its core should be restructured or repacked around the four pillars of learning. These four pillars are learning to know, learning to do, learning to live together and learning to be. This report consists of following seven (7) big concerns about the universal problems.

1. Tension between global and local
2. Tension between universal and individual
3. Tension between tradition and modernity
4. Tension between long term and short term consideration
5. Tension between competition and equality of opportunity
6. Tension between an unlimited expansion of knowledge and the limited capacity of a human being to assimilate
7. Tension between spiritual and material

These tensions are resolved easily, but efforts should be done. Today it is need of the world to do efforts for overcoming the problems of education. Ancient Indian texts are unique sources of knowledge which are helpful for it.

1. Tension between global and local - It is described in Mahopnishada, Sasthodhyaya: 71-75, Ayam Nijah Paroveti Gananaam Laghuchetsaam, Udarcharitanaam Tu Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam. It means we should make efforts globally for humanity, not for an individual. If we succeed to resolve the problem of global education system, it will be the good job for human civilisation. This mission sentence teaches us that the whole universe is like a family.
2. Tension between universal and individual - The shloka of Longakshi Smriti, Sarve Bhavantu Sukhina: Sarve Santu Niramaya:, Sarve Bhadrani Pashyant, Ma Kaschid Dukh Bhag Bhavet favours for the welfare of humanity and wishes for the well-being of everyone which gives the birth to the welfare education. This welfare education awakens the power of knowing oneself and who knows himself, works for the others' welfare.
3. Tension between tradition and modernity - It is written in Skanda Purana (Uttarkaand): Gurugeetaya Prathmoadhyaya that, Gurur Brahma Gurur Vishnu, Gurur Devo

Maheshvarah, Gurur Sakshat Param Brahma, Tasmai Shri Gurve Namah, that means the teacher is creator, guardian and destroyer. Therefore, I salute that teacher who is the ultimate Brahm. Indian tradition teaches us to be a soft heart and to regard our teachers because he only which is above Brahma (the god of creation), Vishnu (the god of nurturing) and Mahesh (the destroyer). To resolve the tension between tradition, technique and modernity we should believe in Devpitrikaryabhyam Na Pramadityyam.

4. Tension between long term and short term consideration - The shloka of Hitopdesha, Vidvatam Ch Nripatvam Ch Naiv Tulyam Kadachan, Swadeshe Poojyate Raja Vidwan Sarvatra Poojyate gives a suggestion of learning by doing and learning by insight. Because fear and force provide respect for the short term while knowledge earns forever. The Indian culture never learns a lesson of fear, force and fight. It teaches to win hearts by knowledge.
5. Tension between competition and equality of opportunity - Today the learner feels education as burden every time due to the wrong choice of subject, pressure of position, family reputation, economic status and competition with colleagues etc. After of hundred tries, when he fails. He tries to wrong steps. Ancient Indian education system gives the opportunity to resolve these tensions. It envisages the thought of Vidya Dhanam Shreshthtaram Tanmoolmitraddham, Daanen Vardhate Nityam Na Bharay Na Niyate in Shloka-123 of Tritiya Adhyaya of Shukraniti.
6. Tension between the unlimited expansion of knowledge and the limited capacity of a human being to assimilate - It is described in Taitireeyopnishada that Ekoaham Bahushyam means I am one and want to be very much. The god provides infinite powers to every person, but it is only need of recognizing. The revelation Satyam Gyanmanantam Brahm of Taitireeyopnishada expresses that the Brahma knowledge or knowledge by experience is the true and infinite knowledge.
7. Tension between spiritual and material - It is said in the shloka, Satyam Vad Dharmam Char Swadhyanma Pramad of Taitireeyopnishada, Bhag-11 which gives the message to stay on truth and behave according to Dharma. This is the way to resolve the tension between spiritual and material. The Upanishad says that Dharma should be decided according to the work area of the person. For examples Dharma for a teacher should be teaching and same as learning for the learner, administration for the administrator, cleaning for cleaner, writing for writer etc. Our culture and traditions teach us to respects our elders, equal and younger. Indian culture also teaches us to respect to mother, father and guru as a god. As it envisages in shloka of Taitireeyopnishada as follows - Matri Devo Bhava, Pitri Devo Bhava, Acharya Devo Bhava, Atithi Devo Bhava, Yanyanvadyani Karmani, Tani Savitvyani, No Itrani.

Conclusion

The roots of knowledge are in the depths of our Indian culture. Only need to recognise and to assimilate. To prepare and to implement a curriculum, many problems are faced by the policy-maker, teacher educators, teachers and learners due to the absence or lack of teaching and learning resources. It will also face difficulties when it is not evaluated properly. Therefore, from the top to bottom, it is needed to invest in the curriculum to face

challenges and to make new strategies to glibness the education. Friedrich Wilhelm Nietzsche (2007), the famous German philosopher wrote that "...dancing in all its forms cannot be excluded from the curriculum of all noble education; dancing with the feet, with ideas, with words, and, need I add that one must also be able to dance with the pen that one must learn how to write? (p. 47)." If we want to make a global curriculum, then we need to diversify the teaching approaches by making colleague-colleague interaction, by multilingual interaction in classroom, by teacher-teacher interaction, by teacher-administration interaction, by demonstration, by experimental exercises, by giving projects in groups, by preparing learners for self-discipline, by group discussions, by taking help to arrange assistive devices carefully in self-presence. In the word of Sri Aurobindo, "The Indians must have the firm faith that India must rise and be great and that everything that happened, every difficulty, every reverse must help and further their end... he dawn would soon be complete, and the sun rises over the horizon. The sun of India's destiny would rise and fill all India with its light and overflow India and overflow Asia and overflow the world." Today it is time to give the message of Vedas and Vedangas for giving right direction to the human civilisation.

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